

Digital Preservation Storage Criteria Update

Informing a New Usage Guide for the Community

History

2015:
Working group formed
iPRES 2015

Workshops, feedback, presentations

2016:
iPRES 2016

2017:
LIBRARY LIBRARY OF CONGRESS

pasig 2017
iPRES 2017

2018:
iPRES 2018

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2019:
PASIG 2019
iPRES 2019

2020-2021:
IFLA

SAA SOCIETY OF AMERICAN ARCHIVISTS
NDSA DIGITAL PRESERVATION

iPRES 2021
17th International Conference on Digital Preservation

iPRES 2025

2nd version of criteria published

3rd version of criteria + usage guide published

4th version of criteria

Digital Preservation Storage Criteria

Criteria	Category	Description	Related Standards
Integrity checking	Content integrity	Performs verifiable and/or auditable checks to detect changes or loss in or across copies (e.g. checksum recalculation, fixity checking, identifying missing files)	ISO 15801 ISO 16363
Cost-efficient	Cost considerations	Costs relatively less overall than other comparable solutions, by being designed with cost efficiencies, for example, has resource pooling and sharing, multi-tenancy (multiple users share the same applications)	ISO 16363 ISO 17797
...

Standards mapping

Standard	Description
ISO 14721	Reference model for an archival information system (OAIS)
ISO 16363	Audit and certification of trustworthy digital repositories
...	...

Play the Game

Learn about the Digital Preservation Storage Criteria using the game.

Learn more

Read more about the Digital Preservation Storage Criteria, and participate in the development

Usage guide

Motivation: Using the Digital Preservation Storage Criteria requires context that is grounded in digital preservation principles

Existing topics:

Risk management

Mitigate loss of data through risk management

Elements in establishing bit safety

Number of copies, Independence between copies and Integrity checks

Independence between copies

Mitigates risk that an event, an agent or technology can harm several copies of data

Costs

The more effectively risks are mitigated, the more preservation storage may cost

Potential New topics

Documentation and Logging

This section includes the following topics:

- Change management processes
- Documentation of infrastructure components and inter-relationships
- Audit trail documentation
- Logging data documentation
- Business continuity and disaster recovery documentation

Preservation Strategy and Technology Review

This section covers the following topics:

- Technology migration
- Format migration
- Media obsolescence
- Energy usage management and planning
- Technology Watch/Environmental Scans

Organizational Operations

This section includes the following topics:

- Organizational planning processes
- Service level agreements (SLAs) and Contracting processes
- Organizational policies for management of data
- Organizational policies for management of infrastructure
- Organizational roles and responsibilities
- Organizational resilience planning processes

System Security and Auditing

This section covers the following topics:

- Preservation storage security management
- Integration of security for preservation storage with other relevant systems
- Auditing and audit trail requirements

Storage Media Management

This section covers the following topics:

- Media traceability and supply chain documentation
- Physical media selection and management
- Media storage conditions

Vocabulary/Glossary

Commonly used terms and their sources

Give you vote and comment!

